

Human-centred Web-based Modelling Tool

The interaction between various fields is rapidly increasing with a growing demands of software, resulting in lots of people from different areas taking part in the software engineering projects. This growth leads to issues on how to coordinate all participants, due to the different levels of IT knowledge of the participants. This research project presents model-driven approach as the key component to resolve such issues between Medical and IT areas.

Based on the findings from literature review, we present our plan of presenting a human-centered web-based modelling platform to help people from all disciplines to get involved in e-health software engineering projects. This survey aims to find out the fundamental user requirements of e-health applications and modeling tools, in order to commence our project towards the correct direction.

* Indicates required question

Informed consent

I have been asked to take part in the research project specified above. I have read and understood the Explanatory Statement and I hereby consent to participate in this project.

1. I agree to the informed consent. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

Other: _____

2. The data that I provide during this research may be used by the investigators in future research projects.

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Personal Detail

To benefit further analysis and exploration, we would like to collect more background information about all participants. Your response are anonymous and safe.

3. What is your pronouns? *

Mark only one oval.

- He/Him/His
- She/Her/Her
- They/Them/Their
- Prefer not to reply

4. What is your age? *

Mark only one oval.

- On behalf of < 18
- 18 - 25
- 26 - 35
- 36 - 45
- 46 - 55
- > 55

5. Where do you live? *

Mark only one oval.

- Australia
- Other: _____

6. Which language do you mainly speak at home? *

Mark only one oval.

English

Other: _____

7. Are you in industry or university? *

Mark only one oval.

University

Business/Industry

Both

Other: _____

8. If you are in industry/business, what is your role?

Mark only one oval.

Software developer

Computer network architects

Computer support specialists

IT project managers

Web developers

Information security analysts

Computer systems analysts

Database administrators and architects

Other: _____

9. If you are in university, are you academic staff or student?

Mark only one oval.

- Staff
- Student
- Other: _____

10. If you are in university, what is your major?

Mark only one oval.

- Computer Science
- Information Technology
- Artefact Intelligence
- Data Science
- Software Engineering
- Cyber Security
- Other: _____

eHealth Application

eHealth is the use of information and communication technology to support health and healthcare, for example telemedicine, smartphone Apps, and wearable sensors.

11. How familiar are you with the concept of eHealth? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1 2 3 4 5
-
- Unf: Familiar
-

12. Explain your reasons for giving that rank.

13. Have you ever used eHealth applications? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

14. If you said yes to the previous question, can you list eHealth apps/websites you have used before?

15. Why did you access to eHealth applications or websites? *

Tick all that apply.

- Searching health-related information
- Finding health practitioners
- Booking appointments
- Other: _____

16. Do you have any other requirements that are not listed in the question above regarding the eHealth apps?

You can see screenshots and links to four different eHealth applications below.

[Healthengine](#)

HealthHub

Login

Health A-Z

Live Healthy

Mental Well-Being

Parent Hub

Health Programmes

Health Services

Enjoy quick access with biometrics or passcode

Health Services

Appointments

Lab Results

Covid-19 Records

Payments

Immunisation

More Services →

HotDoc

List your practice Search Log in / Sign up

Book your next healthcare appointment

Find, book and add your favourite practitioners to your care team.

Specialty or provider name Suburb or postcode

- Popular General Practitioner, Dentist, Optometrist, Physiotherapist, Psychologist, Radiologist, Podiatrist
- Telehealth General Practitioner, Physiotherapist, Psychologist

Are you a GP, dentist, specialist or allied health provider?

List your practice on HotDoc

New

Find a COVID-19 vaccine

[Peking University First Hospital Portal](#)

17. Please pick one of the four eHealth applications shown earlier based on the colour you liked the most and answer to the following questions. Which app did you select? (You can also add another application if you use eHealth apps)

Mark only one oval.

- Healthengine
- HealthHub
- HotDoc
- Peking University First Hospital Portal
- Other: _____

18. Do you think the UI style of the selected eHealth app is comfortable or easily identifiable?

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree or disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

19. Do you think the text on your selected eHealth apps is large enough to be read clearly? *

Mark only one oval.

- Too large for me
- Large for me
- I don't have any issues
- Small for me
- Too small for me

20. What kind of colours do you prefer to use on the eHealth application?

Mark only one oval.

- Cool colors
- Warm colors
- Other: _____

21. Which size of text do you prefer to use on the eHealth application? *

10pt

12pt

14pt

18pt

22pt

26pt

30pt

34pt

38pt

Mark only one oval.

10pt

12pt

14pt

18pt

22pt

26pt

30pt

34pt

38pt

Other: _____

22. Which icon style on eHealth apps is better for you? *

Mark only one oval.

- Left one
- Middle one
- Right one

Transition section

23. If you want to take part in the next part which is about visual-based modeling, you should choose 'Yes', otherwise, you can choose 'No' to end this survey.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes *Skip to question 24*
- No *Skip to section 7 (Submit Your Response)*

Software Modelling Experience

Software Modelling is a high-level methodology to build simplified prototypes through abstracting feature of software systems.

24. Do you know visual modeling? *

*Visual modeling: is the graphic representation of problems and systems of interest using graphical languages. It is a way for the experts and novices to have a common understanding of otherwise complicated ideas.

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

25. Have you ever drawn or viewed a visual modeling diagram like shown below? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

26. Thinking of the visual modelling graphics you have read before, do you think they are clear to understand easily?

Mark only one oval.

- Very clear
- Clear
- Neutral
- Unclear
- Very Unclear

27. If they are hard to understand, please share us with your reasons.

28. Have you ever experienced modelling tools before? *

e.g. Lucid Chart

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

29. Can you list modelling tools you have used before?

30. Thinking of your recent experience of using a modelling tool, can you rate its accessibility

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Bad Good

31. Can you share more about your experience of using modeling tools?

32. Would you like to distinguish different classes by shape or colour? *

Mark only one oval.

- A. Colour
- B. Shape
- C. Special Icon
- Other: _____

33. If you are required to assign colors for your items in visual modeling graphic, which colour would you like to choose from below chart?

Tick all that apply.

- Yellow
- Yellow-Orange
- Orange
- Red-Orange
- Red
- Red-Violet
- Violet
- Blue-Violet
- Blue
- Blue-Green
- Green
- Yellow-Green

34. Please show your thoughts about the importance of each feature in modeling tools. *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly unnecessary	unnecessary	Nuetral	Necessary	Strongly Necessary
Proper text size	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clear colours	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Recognizable icons	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Code generation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
User guideline	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Skip to section 7 (Submit Your Response)

Submit Your Response

Please do not forget submitting your response when you are ready. Thanks for your participation!

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